

Geothermal characteristics of the Biyo Kulule Hot springs in Bosasso, Somalia

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ABSTRACT

Biyo Kulule geothermal prospect in Bossaso region is the first geothermal site ever considered for development in Somalia. The site is characterized by medium temperature hot springs that discharge along geologic structures. Geochemical assessment of the thermal spring indicate that the fluid circulating in the sediments is preferentially of Na-Cl-SO₄ type with appreciable amounts of CO₂, F, and K. Equilibrium temperature yield values spanning between 150 to 220 °C pointing to a possible existence of an intermediate (medium enthalpy) geothermal system. In addition, the Biyo Kulule geothermal fluid samples have relatively low PCO₂; this may perhaps be reflecting minimal or no influence of deep CO₂ sources that is typical of EARS degassing and exsolution of hydrothermal-magmatic systems. It is anticipated that the resource at Biyo Kulule is capable of generating electricity from an ORC system and as well provide for direct use applications. The developer is planning to undertake detailed surface studies that will lead to drilling of exploration and production wells. The project is potentially feasible due to the very high electricity tariffs in Puntland that exceeds US\$40 cts to US\$1/kWhr.

1. Introduction

Despite being located in Eastern Africa, Somalia, which characterize the “horn of Africa” is not considered as belonging to the African Rift System (EARS), where geothermal resources are known to occur. It was therefore not considered as a target for geothermal development. This results from the fact that Somalia is considered by the geological community as a continental plate, sub-plate of the African continent, that is essentially a stable platform lacking geothermal manifestations.

Biyo Kulule (BK) is the first geothermal site ever considered for development in Somalia, and more precisely in Puntland, the easternmost part of Somalia. No site had ever been considered for its geothermal potential until now in Somalia. The nearest known geothermal site is Asal, in Djibouti Republic, more than 500 km away to the West.

1. Geodynamic environment of Biyo Kulule geothermal site

Puntland is the north-eastern most extremity of the African continent, and if the coast of the Indian Ocean extending south of the horn (with Socotra Island as the easternmost extension of the Somalian plate) is much wider, it is a rather stable continental shelf, whereas the northern coastline sits along the southern border of the Gulf of Aden, which is an active rift. Along the Aden Ridge, the spreading rate is over 2 cm a year, that is 10 times faster than the Kenya Rift Valley, with a huge amount of heat released along its axis. The geodynamics of Gulf of Aden

(Fig. 2) is characterized by numerous short spreading segments, of WNW-ESE direction, connected by transform faults trending NE-SW, controlled by fracture zones of the same direction. These fracture zones affecting this ocean floor - made of mid-oceanic ridge basalts (MORB) - extend until the continent, where normal faults parallel to the spreading segments are also observed.

Fig.1: Geographic map of Northern Somalia showing the location of the BK geothermal site (green square) selected for this project, 10 Km East from Bossaso, the capital of Puntland

Fig.2 : Geodynamic structure of the Gulf of Aden, an active mid-oceanic rift. Socotra Island is the Easternmost extension of the Somalian plate. Colors are ranging from blue to red showing the age of the sea floor from the oldest (18 My) to the youngest (present). The active spreading axis is shown in white. Spreading segments are divided by Transform Faults and Fracture zones (red lines). The Biyo Kulule (BK) geothermal site is figured with a red filled circle, sitting along the southern extension of a major fracture zone (from Fournier et al., 2010).

When observing the geology of the Somalian cost-line (Fig.3 and 4), we see that BK geothermal site is dominantly controlled by normal faults of WNW-ESE direction, parallel to the oceanic ridge axis (described in Fig.2). These are of Mio-Pliocene age, affecting sedimentary units of Jurassic and Cretaceous era. Combined with a NE-SW fracture zone, the

BK geothermal site is clearly controlled by this double fracture system inherited from the nearby active Aden ridge.

Fig. 3: Geological map of the BK geothermal site (red quadrangle), located in the vicinity of Boosaaso, township and port along the Aden coast line. Observe the WNW-ESE faulting controlling the geothermal emergences which also sit along a NE-SW discontinuity (fracture zone, dotted red). Modified from Geological map of Somalia (Abbate et al., 1994).

Fig. 4: Legend of the Geological maps (from Abbate et al., 1994)

2. Geography and topography

The BK site is located to the East of Boosaaso ([11° 17' 00" north, 49° 10' 00" east](#)), as seen in Fig. 1). It is the most important town and port of Puntland, populated over 1 Million inhabitants. Since the Somalian Civil war, in the 1990, Bossaso became the administrative and political capital of Puntland, which is the north-easternmost part of Somalia. It now acts as a major port between the Persian Gulf and the Red Sea (and Mediterranean through the Suez Canal). It is also the maritime terminal of a highway for the export of cattle from East-Africa (Somalia and Ethiopia in particular) to middle East. A strong population increase in the last 30 years is in particular due to migration from Mogadishu. As a consequence, the township and port may even reach 2 Million people.

The main problem of Bossaso is the access to water and energy (electricity and cooling); the total power production installed did not exceed 16 MWe in 2019; the identification of a geothermal resource is therefore a major issue. The area is rather arid, with a relatively barren vegetation. BK site is well known locally, as the thermal springs are abundant and used for baths and recreational purposes. The water flow is so abundant that it benefits to a natural beautiful vegetation, while pasturelands and agricultural production developed in the vicinity.

As seen on the DEM model (Fig. 5 and 7) and satellite imagery (Fig. 6) the geothermal area selected for the project (green quadrangle) is located 7 Km East from Bossaso township (10 Km from town centre). The coordinates of the site are: 11°17'52.0"N 49°12'54.0"E. The thermal emergences sit at the intersection of two major structural patterns, well visible in the regional DEM: the NE-SW fracture zone, which marks a major geological discontinuity reported in red in Fig. 3, and a set of normal faults of WSW-ENE direction with strata dipping towards the Gulf defining a long marginal graben extending over nearly 50 Km to the East (with a wide aquifer serving the port and city of Qandala).

Fig. 5: DEM map of the BK (green quadrangle) site surroundings, near the city and port of Bossaso to the west and the wide marginal graben feeding the aquifer observed to the East.

Fig.6: Satellite imagery of the BK site (green quadrangle), located East from Bossaso, and sitting in the middle of a graben at the latitude of 70m, surrounded by cliffs up to 500m high, open west and therefore easily accessible from Bossaso, with a good road. Major faults are reported in red.

Fig. 7: Detailed DEM map of the BK site (green quadrangle). The geothermal indices are located at an altitude of 70m asl in a depressed area (70 to 120m asl) surrounded by hills up to 500m high. The emergences and topographic discontinuities are controlled by faults of WNW-ESE to NW-SE direction crossed by faults trending NE-SW to ENE-WSW.

3. Geology

The geology of the area is dominated by the general context described above, which characterizes the continental margins of the Gulf of Aden. The sedimentary sequence, from early Jurassic to late Cretaceous, covering the Pre-Mesozoic basement of the Afro-Arabian shield (late Panafrican Orogeny, with greenschist metamorphic facies and associated plutonic intrusion; Varet, 2022), was faulted in a NW-SE to WNW-ESE direction due to an early extension event predating the opening of the Gulf of Aden. In addition, NE-SW trending major discontinuities (fracture zones), also marking the shore-lines on both sides of the Gulf, characterize this early structural pattern which also marks the major spreading discontinuities. And as a consequence, similar units and structural patterns are observed on both sides of the Gulf, along the Southern Arabian plate margin (in Yemen) and Northern Somalian plate margin.

a. Structural geology

The BK site is therefore controlled by these two sets of faults: the dominantly visible WNW-ESE normal faults, and the NE-SW fracture zones. Both structural patterns are inherited from pre-rift geology and still act as geodynamic components of the present Gulf of Aden spreading system.

b. Volcanology

On both sides of this FZ, two volcanic eruption centres are observed (as seen on the geological map in Fig. 3), made of basaltic flows sitting in grabens near the sea side. These magmatic units are postdating the major faults but are eventually affected by more recent (Pleistocene) normal faults. Detailed views of these volcanic units are seen in Fig.8. These could be taken as signs of potential magmatic heat sources at depth in the BK site surroundings. But the age of these events are not dated yet, not allowing to ensure that these are young enough. Similarly, the petrographic nature of the events also needs to be précised, in order to show if a differentiation process operated. These are the two conditions for a reliable magmatic heat source.

Fig. 8: The two Pleistocene volcanic districts located West (upper image, near Boosaano) and East (near Qandala, lower image) of the BK site. Rather recent basaltic flows emitted from WNW-ESE trending faults cover a surface of circa 400km² on each site, showing signs of potential magmatic heat source at depth (extract from satellite imagery).

c. Sedimentary stratigraphy

The geological sequence characterizing the BK area is well established; a typical section is shown in Fig.9, showing the continental margin structure and sequence. It was well studied, as these sedimentary units are also targets for oil exploration, and were crossed by a few exploration wells drilled along the Gulf of Aden margins. The location of the nearest oil well (called Laasqorail) is seen in Fig.3. It shows a sedimentary sequence – also observed in fault escarpments near Boossaso –from Neogene to Jurassic, up to 4.000 m thick. The whole sequence is dominantly of marine origin, with abundant limestones, and silts and clays intercalations. Volcanic events are also observed, in particular in the Pliocene (marking the Gulf opening) and Pleistocene, showing that the continental margin locally active, as seen around the BK site. The whole sedimentary sequence, from Neogene to Jurassic, with indices for each unit used in the geological map is detailed in Table 1.

Fig.9: Geological section of the Gulf of Aden margin in northern Somalia showing the sequence crossed by an oil well at Laasqoray; location seen west of the BK site in Fig.2 (From Abbate et al.,: 1994). Observe the block normal faulting dipping towards the Gulf Axis, and tilting southward, towards the continent, as observed locally at BK site.

d. The geological system of the BK site

The BK system do not belong to the classical high temperature model, with a caprock produced by self-sealing (clay cap and impermeable hydrothermal deposits). We rely here upon a fault-controlled system affecting sedimentary units, building a thick sequence of permeable (karstic limestones, eventually sands and gravels) and impermeable (clay, shales and marls) lithologic units, as seen on the geological map of Fig. 10 and related geological section of Fig.15.

The Jurassic karstic limestones are believed to act as excellent geothermal reservoirs, even if the geothermal fluid up-flow is most probably issued from the deeper fractured basement, as shown from water geochemistry.

Fig.10: Geological map of the BK geothermal site (red square), showing the dominantly WNW-ESE normal faulting, the NE-SW fracture zone marking a major geological discontinuity, and the sedimentary sequences in the faulted blocks ranging from Jurassic (blue) to Neogene (grey). In red is shown a syenite intrusion; basalts are also seen, near Qandala, in brown. The trace of the geological cross section through BK geothermal site of Fig. 15 is shown in blue. From Abbate et al. (1994).

The geological section of Fig.11 shows the location of the BK thermal emergences in a lateral graben bounded by normal faults on both sides, North and South. The floor of the graben is itself heavily faulted, with open faulting favoring the up-flow of the geothermal fluids issued from the Jurassic limestone intermediate reservoir, itself fed by deep-seated faults affecting the pre-Mesozoic basement.

4. Surface geothermal manifestations

The Biyo Kulule geothermal site (green square on Fig.16) is characterized by emergences of hot-springs, emitted from the faulted sedimentary sequence described above. The hot-springs area (in the blue oval) merge from a low-land area (70-120m asl) surrounded North and South by cliffs up to 500m high. Two major sets of faults dominate the area, trending WNW-ESE and NW-SE, which characterize the Gulf of Aden geodynamic system.

Fig. 11: N-S geological cross section through the Biyo Kulule geothermal site. Same color legend as the geological map of Fig.10, where the location of the section is shown in blue.

Fig.12: Structural map of the BK area (green square), as seen from satellite imagery, showing the dominant structural trends controlling the marginal graben from the floor of which the thermal springs emerge (blue ellipse).

We propose a progressive zoom on the BK area:

- While at a 10 Km scale (Fig.13 a), we observe these two sets of major regional faults described above, at a 4 Km scale (Fig.13b), we clearly observe the graben controlled by sub-E-W arcuate faults (resulting from combined regional faults seen above) and NW-SE faults limiting the system west.
- At a Km scale map (Fig.13c), it is possible to analyze the structure of the graben floor, specifically controlling the thermal manifestations. It appears that both NW-SE normal faults, intersecting with E-W faults control the emergences.
- At a smaller scale, the thermal manifestations appear on the satellite image in dark green color, (as seen at a 500m scale on Fig.13c), due to the abundant vegetation of the ecosystem resulting from these emergences.

Fig.13a: zoom on the BK site (4Km scale), located in a graben, with major E-W arcuate faults bordering the graben North and South, and NW-SE faults to the west. The thermal emergences are seen in dark green.

Fig.13b: structural pattern observed on the graben floor, at 1Km scale. Observe the dominant NW-SE normal faults with also E-W faults, both clearly controlling the emergences. Whereas the out-flow follows the NW direction of the wadies (themselves fault-controlled), the up-flow zones appear as aligned E-W, the direction of the major graben.

Fig. 13c: Detailed view on a satellite image (500m scale) of the BK thermal manifestations, which emerge from wadies floors. The green colour results from the vegetation that develop thanks to the surface and ground-water flow. It merge along a fault-controlled E-W up-flow zone, with outflow towards NW along wadies sedimentary fillings themselves controlled by the regional fault pattern.

At this detailed scale, it appears that if the Biyo Kulule thermal site, 300x70m wide, elongated in the NW-SE direction, is the main geothermal index, it appears that other emergences are observed to the East and South, mostly as shallow groundwater and wet soils, over an E-W length of 2 Km and a N-S width of 700 metres. That is 1,5 square kilometres. We hypothesize an up-flow zone controlled by the intersection of the E-W faults that characterize the walls of this local graben, with the NW-SE normal faults affecting the graben floor. Near the surface, an out-flow develops towards north, controlled by the detritic sediments pattern of the wadies flowing towards NW under fault-controlled lineaments. As a result, whereas located in a desertic environment, the area appears as an oasis with a luxurious vegetation, with planted parts and resort area, used as popular bathing area. The water sampled from Biyo Kulule (BK) spring was analyzed in order to provide geochemical insights on the geothermal resource of this geothermal site. This allowed to classify the water using the ubiquitous trilinear diagram and to determine the equilibrium temperature based on solute geothermometers. The analysis, data processing and interpretation are detailed in the chapter entitled “*Reservoir*” below. We can mention here the major conclusions which are drawn from the interpretation and synthesis of these available geochemistry results. Data clearly suggest the presence of a geothermal reservoir hosting a low to intermediate and eventually high temperature within the precincts of the Biyo Kulule area:

- Whereas the surface indices are limited to hot geothermal water emergence, without fumarole or high temperature indices;
- The water are of Na-Cl type, implying a link with the Gulf of Aden geodynamic system;
- The estimated equilibrium reservoir temperature span between 140 to 210 °C thus pointing to a possible existence of intermediate to high temperature system

Conclusion concerning the surface manifestations

The known surface geothermal manifestations on site are hot springs and ground-water up-flows and out-flows extending over a surface of 1,5 square kilometres, in a graben controlled by a set of faults that result from the Gulf of Aden opening, and which are reactivated by the active spreading along the Gulf axis (over 2 centimetres a year). No fumarole or direct sign of high temperature geothermal system is observed, although the surface survey of the hydrothermal alterations and deposits needs further field and laboratory analysis. But the chemistry of the thermal spring water clearly indicate a possible medium and eventually high temperature reservoir, which, if confirmed, would allow for electricity production, a highly demanded resource in the Bossaso township, with circa 2 million inhabitants deprived until now of sustainable renewable energy source. The geological sequence, well known thanks to oil research and exploration drilling in the region, indicate thick sedimentary sequence (4.000 metres thick), with at depth an important Jurassic limestone reservoir, a few hundred metres thick, that could host a significant geothermal resource. Of interest to note that the composition of the geothermal water do not indicate a carbonaceous composition, as expected in such environment, but a chloride character that may indicate a slight contribution of marine origin. This in turn may support the idea of a fault-controlled reservoir connecting at depth with the Gulf of Aden active telluric axis, hence feeding the BK geothermal system at depth.

5. Geothermal conceptual modeling

According to the classical model of geothermal systems, the present geological reconnaissance allows to establish a first scheme of the BK geothermal system. It remains essentially qualitative at this stage as no well data nor geophysics allows to document precisely the vertical dimension (i.e. the 3D modeling) of the system.

a. The Heat source

The question of the nature of the heat source at BK site is not fully elucidated yet.

- Of course, we are not in presence of a central volcano, with differentiated products that would indicate a local, shallow depth magmatic heat source.
- But if we are in presence of a non-volcanic low-temperature resource, fault controlled, given the surface conditions, we cannot exclude a connection of the surface manifestations with a significant heat source in the Gulf of Aden active system.
- It is even reasonable to consider that such medium or even high temperature conditions may prevail in this geodynamic environment. In particular the fault-control of the BK site which is directly produced by the Gulf of Aden geodynamics. We have also these two recent volcanic fields surrounding the site, the age and precise nature of which needs to be elucidated. These also show not only purely tectonic controlled geothermal system but also existing magmatic connections with the oceanic ridge.

We should here underline that the BK geothermal project will be the first in Africa located in such a geological context of active oceanic rift margin. We know that oceanic ridges are the most efficient geothermal systems on earth, with geothermal heat flow 10 times higher than in normal gradient areas. That is up to 30°C per 100 metres, allowing for high temperature resources at 1 km depth. Of course, the site is not located on the spreading ridge itself, but certainly benefits from its thermal influence, particularly through the major Fracture Zone (FZ) observed here (as shown in orange in Fig.10). We know that this FZ controls the Transform Fault (TF) that connects the active rift segments in the Aden Ridge spreading axis. From the point of view of the geothermal perspective in Africa at large, besides the achievement of the BK site answering the need of Bossaso regional capital and grid, the success in this exploration and development project would undoubtedly boost the development of geothermal initiatives all along the north-eastern African plate margin (Red Sea and Aden coastline in particular).

b. The reservoir

The reservoir at Biyo Kulule (BK) is clearly controlled by the fault systems described above. The NE-SW fracture zone which directly links the site with the Gulf of Aden spreading axis intersects the WNW-ESE trending normal faulting which dominates the structure of the region. Locally, these combined regional structural patterns form a graben, controlled by sub-E-W major faults, whereas the thermal emergences are aligned on lineaments of the same direction, whereas the graben floor where the hot-springs emerge is affected by a set of faults on WNW-ESE direction.

c. Fluid geochemistry

The water sampled from Biyo Kulule (BK) spring was analysed in order to provide geochemical insights on the geothermal resource of this geothermal site. This allowed to classify the water using the ubiquitous trilinear diagram and to determine the equilibrium temperature based on solute geothermometers.

Chemical analysis were carried out in 2021 and 2022 at an accredited laboratory using methods in accord with international norms and standards. The water samples were analysed for

parameters including: pH, TDS, conductivity, CO₂, Na, K, Ca, Mg, , Cl, F, B, SiO₂, SO₄. Analysis of CO₂ as TCC were carried out titrimetrically using 0.1M HCl as per ASTM Standards D513-82 Vol.11 .01 1988. Analysis of the major aqueous cation components (Na, K, Ca, Mg,) Boron, SO₄ and SiO₂ were done using UV/Vis. Chloride analysis was done titrimetrically using argentometric Mohr’s method using AgNO₃ as per the standards defined in APHA 4500 Cl- D (modified) 22nd Edition 2012 while fluoride was analyzed using ISE as per the standards defined in APHA 4500-F C 22nd Edition 2012. Some analytical results of the water phase components are presented in Table 1. The following data and conclusions are from a detailed geochemistry report by Leakey Ochieng (SEPCO, 2022)

Table 1: Chemistry of water phase components of the Biyo Kulule spring

	pH	Cond.	TDS	CO ₂ (TCC)	SiO ₂	Cl	SO ₄	F	B	Mg	Na	Ca	K
Lab.	pH Scale	µs/cm	mg/l										
1	6.7	1126	563	36	<0.01	184	-	2.14		6.32	289.36	70.54	22.14
2	6.36	1132	567	-	<0.01	148	45	2.14	0.97	-	-	-	-

The BK water is of a near neutral pH of 6.7 and is preferentially enriched in dissolved constituents with a magnitude of 563 mg/kg. Na and Cl are the major dissolved components in the water. The incipient interpretation of the water sample was evaluated in terms of the relation between major anions (HCO₃, SO₄, and Cl) and major cations (Na, K, Ca, and Mg) by means of the triangular diagrams with concentrations in milliequivalents per litre and are presented in Figures 19 and 20, respectively. Equilibrium reservoir temperature of controlling the BK surface spring was done using Na/K, K/Mg and K/Ca functions. Quartz geothermometer could not be adopted owing to the contrastingly low detection of SiO₂ content in the water. The equilibrium temperature based on the selected geothermometer functions of Fournier (1991), Fournier and Truesdell (1973) and Arnórsson et al. (1983) yield values in the range of 140 to 170°C. The results are presented in Table 2.

Table 3: Solute geothermometry

Function	K/Mg	K/Ca	Na/K	Na/K	Na/K
Source	Fournier (1991)	Fournier and Truesdell (1973)	Arnórsson et al. (1983)	Fournier (1991)	Giggenbach (1988)
Equilibrium temperature	150°C	140°C	170°C	200°C	210°C

Conclusions from BK water geochemistry

The following conclusions are drawn from the interpretation and synthesis of available geochemistry. Data suggests the presence of a geothermal reservoir hosting a low to intermediate-temperature within the precincts of the Biyo Kulule area:

- The water are of Na-Cl type
- The estimated equilibrium reservoir temperature span between 140 to 210 °C thus pointing to a possible existence of intermediate to high temperature system

As a whole, while the geothermal ground-water up-flows and out-flows extend over a surface of 1,5 square kilometres, these are controlled by a set of faults that result from the Gulf of Aden opening, and which are reactivated by the spreading (over 2 centimetres a year) occurring along the Gulf axis. The geochemistry of the thermal spring water clearly indicate a possible medium and eventually high temperature reservoir, which, if confirmed, would allow for electricity production, a highly demanded resource in the Boossaso township, over 1 million inhabitants deprived until now of sustainable renewable energy source. The geological sequence, well known thanks to oil research and exploration drilling in the region, indicate thick sedimentary sequence (4.000 metres thick), with at depth an important limestone reservoir, a few hundred metres thick, that could host a significant geothermal resource. However, the composition of the geothermal water do not indicate a carbonaceous composition, as expected in such environment, but a chloride character that may indicate a partly marine origin. This in turn may support the idea of a fault-controlled reservoir connecting at depth with the Gulf of Aden active telluric axis, hence feeding the BK geothermal system at depth.

d. The recharge

While the site area is heavily faulted, with tilted blocks of sedimentary rock-sequences, both allowing for good recharge conditions, we should also consider that the area is really desartic, with very limited rainfall, of the order of 100 mm per year. Therefore, the recharge from meteoritic water is limited despite these favorable conditions. But the site is located rather near to the coast, allowing at depth inflows from marine water, as confirmed by the geochemistry of the hot-springs. Note however that the salinity of the fluids is much lower than sea water, which implies also other sources, most probably meteoritic. The hypothesis concerning the recharge should be better constrained by isotopic analysis. The important and fairly regular outflow of the springs indicate good recharge conditions at present rates. Due to the present lack of existing wells it is not possible yet to further precise the hydrogeological model that should rely upon a study which will need to be engaged in the coming phase. At this stage we should point out that, in case of insufficient water recharge, and eventually in any case, due to the arid conditions that will not improve due to climate change, the geothermal exploitation system should consider the option of reinjection in the reservoir of the whole fluid used at the surface for energy production through an heat exchanger. Meaning that the system will not use direct steam separation but an electricity production using an ORC technology. The chemical quality of the fluid appears as favorable for such an option, as neither excessive corrosion (due to balanced pH) nor deposits (due to dissolved cations) are expected.

e. The cap rock

The BK system do not belong to the classical high temperature model, with a caprock produced by self-sealing (clay cap and impermeable hydrothermal deposits). We rely here upon a fault-controlled system affecting sedimentary units, building a thick sequence of permeable (karstic limestones, eventually sands and gravels) and impermeable (clay, shales and marls) lithologic units, as seen above. The best conditions for the reservoir is certainly the case in which the Jurassic karstic limestone layers, a few hundred metres thick, is also affected by both normal faults and fracture zones, as observed on site. The cap rocks will be abundantly represented (clay, shales and marls layers) in the upper geological sequences (Cretaceous to Neogene), over 1000m thick. As the geothermal reservoir to be exploited will be of at least 1.000m deep, and eventually 2.000 to 3.000 metres, the question of the caprock is not really a problem. The thick sedimentary sequence overlying the reservoir will provide a large amount of aquitards

What is not excluded, and may result of high interest, will be the presence of several aquifers and aquitards in this overlying sequence, allowing for several levels of geothermal water productions, from shallow drinking water to intermediate warm water for direct uses applications, to the deepest reservoir used for electricity production through ORC. This should influence the conception of the drilling program.

6. Synthesis and conceptual model

The conceptual model resulting from the above-described geological conditions is reported in Fig.14 & 15.

Fig. 14: Biyo Kulule geothermal model, seen from the surface. The surface manifestation (hot-spring) emerge from a geothermal reservoir made of karstic Jurassic limestone normally faulted in the WNW-ESE trend that characterize the Gulf of Aden spreading axis and lateral continental shelves of both Arabian (Yemen) and Somalian plates. An important magmatic heat source characterize this fast spreading segment (over 2 cm a year). Lateral flow of both magma and thermal fluids penetrate in the Somalian plate margin through an active NE-SW Fracture Zone feeding both volcanic manifestations and geothermal fluids at the surface and in the sub-surface. A medium to high temperature reservoir developed in the Jurassic limestone at depth at Biyo Kulule geothermal site.

The heat source is derived from high temperature fluids circulating in the NE-SW trending Fracture Zones (FZ) of the Gulf of Aden towards South, along the Somalian Plate northern margin. The BK area is located at the point where these FZ cross the WNW-ESE normally faulted sea coast of the Gulf of Aden. It induced both magmatic diking, surface eruptions and geothermal fluids up-flows and eventually surface thermal manifestations.

Good geothermal reservoir conditions could develop at depth, in the thick karstic Jurassic limestones, also affected by this double-faulting. Very high permeability zones could form, exceptionally connected to the surface through permeable faulting, whereas most reservoir volumes are protected at depth from such up-flow due to the thick sedimentary sequence (from Cretaceous to Neogene), which contains numerous impermeable layers forming an efficient cap.

Fig.15: Geothermal conceptual model of Biyo Kulule seen along a vertical cross section following the NE-SW trending Fracture Zone that links the active magmatic heat source of the Aden Ridge axis to the northern continental shelf and shore line of the Somalian plate margin. The area benefits from fluids flows, both magmatic and hydrothermal which percolate to the surface providing the observed recent volcanic lava fields and the thermal springs of Biyo Kulule. The fractured reservoir is mainly hosted in the Jurassic karstic reservoir, a few hundred metres thick, whereas the overlying sedimentary sequence from Cretaceous to Eocene, up to 3 Km thick offers an efficient cover.

Recharge from surface meteoritic water is limited, whereas sea-water invasion is favored, due to the efficient fracture zones and combined normal faulting. However, the lack of evaporation due to the overlying cap-rocks sediments do not facilitate the development of high salinity brines. The geothermal fluid therefore keeps a balanced pH and moderate salinity, favorable for an exploitation through heat exchanger (of doublet or triplet type) with the total flow being reinjected.

6.1. Preliminary resource evaluation

Data presently available do not allow to propose a quantitative evaluation of the resource. This will be possibly proposed only after the detailed geological (including TG wells and slim holes), geochemical (fluids, rock-water interactions), and geophysical (gravimetry, MT) surveys will be completed. For instance, the 1,5 square kilometres surface where surface manifestations are observed should be taken as a minimal indication, as the extension of the reservoir at depth could be much wider, and hidden due to the thick sedimentary sequence overlying the Jurassic limestone reservoir. In addition, the respective role of the fracture zones, versus formation permeability cannot be précised at this stage. Such quantitative evaluation will be provided after the surface studies proposed in the present application.

7. Conclusion

The Byio Kulule Geothermal site represents a new geothermal “play type” with respect to those already identified, explored and demonstrated elsewhere in the East-African Rift System (EARS). It neither belongs to the volcanic systems of the Eastern Branch, nor to the tectonic system of the Western Branch. It also differs from sedimentary systems identified elsewhere, as in Tanzania. This site however displays indices that let open the option to consider the potential development of medium to high geothermal enthalpy potential. Of course, the most evident perspective could be to consider a low-enthalpy system allowing to exploit the important outflow of hot water observed on site for direct uses applications. But given the high demand for electricity and energy for cooling and air conditioning in the country - and in particular in the Bossaso capital - located at a few kilometres from the BK site, in a potentially exceptionally favorable geothermal environment.

The present geological reconnaissance allowed to identify specific geodynamic conditions of high potential geothermal interest, prevailing along the active fracture zones cutting through the entire Aden Ridge, and combined normal faulting parallel to the active rift axis. The surface studies proposed should allow to confirm the hypothesis and open a real perspective of development for this part of Somaliland with encounter a dramatic energy shortage. site.

In case of success, this operation should allow for duplications of the model on other similar geothermal play-types along the active oceanic margins of the Red Sea and Gulf of Aden.

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